

METHODS AND WAYS OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF HISTORY OF IRAN FOR STUDENTS LEARNING THE PERSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The experience of teaching Arabic and Persian makes teachers of this direction turn to new ways and methods of teaching in order to conduct training in accordance with the requirements of the time. The purpose of the subject and the objective of the subject is to study the issues of increasing the level of students' knowledge of the history of Iran, certain periods of the history of the Persian people, enriching students' knowledge of the history, economy and politics of Iran in the 15th-21st centuries, as well as the formation of the basic concepts of the periods covered by the study of Iranian history. The subject of Iranian history includes the political situation of Iran in the Middle Ages - from the 15th-21st centuries, the dynasties of kings of this period, the economic and political relations of Iran with other countries, the current state of the country and its position in the process of events in the modern world.

Key words: teaching methods, history, subject, students, Iran.

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The period of independence of our country brought about a new stage in the political and cultural life of Tajikistan in the development and progress of the society, which is also reflected in the field of education. Among other things, it is worth noting the expansion of the fields of meteorology during this period. In the conditions of globalization of information and economic and cultural integration, the need for language learning and language skills is increasing to join this process of the 21st century.

The establishment of the Faculty of Oriental Languages at the State Technical University «Khujand state University named after academician Bobojon Gafurov» was a cultural phenomenon of the republic and a response to the implementation of the instructions of the President of Tajikistan on the study of foreign languages and languages of the world. It has been 20 years since the teachers of the faculty have been working in the implementation of these instructions. The teachers of Arabic, Persian and Chinese languages have a responsible task to teach students the skills of learning a foreign language more and better and to contribute to the implementation of the following wisdom:

If you know three hundred languages, it is not too much.

It doesn't hurt if it all works one day.

Today, the instruction of the Leader of the Nation obliges teachers to focus on the important issues of education: «Issues of increasing the quality of education and training, humanizing information, the latest teaching methods, the application of computer technology in the educational process, which is one of the primary requirements of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic «Tajikistan and the chairmanship of the «Khujand state University named after academician Bobojon Gafurov», and also cooperation with the education departments of city and regional executive bodies, general education

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schools are in the center of attention of the chairmanship and the faculty community» [3, p.5].

- Iran's history is in step with all world studies;
- its study contributes to the formation of students' knowledge and outlook on the history of this country, enriching the student's knowledge and information;
- has an important role in cultivating a sense of pride in the value of the culture and history of the country of the language of study».

The purpose of the subject and the task of the subject is to study issues of increasing the level of students' knowledge of the history of Iran, certain periods of the history of the Persian people, enriching the students' knowledge of the history, economy and politics of Iran in the 15th-21st centuries, as well as the formation of the main concepts of the periods covered study of Iranian history. In the implementation of this task, the teachers try as much as possible to introduce the students to the modern ways and means of education. For the purposeful transition of education, we turn to the requirements and pillars of today's lesson:

1. Use of visualization in education;
2. Relating the topics to the present time;
3. Application of computer technology, technical means of education in the educational process;
4. Ensuring connection between disciplines;
5. Organization and implementation of students' practical work.

A teacher of a higher school should use more ways and means to make his lesson meaningful and interesting. In this case, we provide an explanation of the above requirements:

1. The use of visualization in the lesson of the history of Iran (complex of methodical education) [2] serves as the main material, which was developed on the basis of the materials of the series of educational journals of the history of Iran (ancient, middle and modern) 1377 [2, p.187-190]. At the same time, the history lesson requires that, of course, illustrated maps are used in the lesson, and some maps of the country of Iran and individual cities such as Tehran, Shiraz, Tabrez, Isfahan, Mashhad, which are available, will help us a lot as a guide.

2. Relating the topics to the present time is one of the serious requirements of the modern lesson, which the teacher must take into account and apply in the educational activity. During the teaching of the history of Iran, the state of the country in the current conditions, the position of Iran in the political situation of the world, the issues of Iran's nuclear weapons, which in the last few years have caused the country's intense relations with the United States and other superpowers of the world, political relations and cooperation between Tajikistan and Iran. in the post-independence era, it is appropriate and the goal. It should be emphasized that the expansion of political relations has a positive effect on the development of economic and cultural cooperation. An example of this cooperation between Tajikistan and Iran in the field of road construction, tunneling, launching joint industrial enterprises of Tajikistan and Iran in our republic, the visit of poets and scientists of these two countries, cooperation in the field of science, medicine, trade and other spheres of life, which should be mentioned in the lessons. suitable for the purpose.

This work is also important from the point of view that students show interest in existing global issues and at the same time get additional information about the country of the language of study.

3. Scientific technical media, application of computer technology in the learning process is a serious requirement of education, and teachers are required to work regularly in this direction. Today, taking this requirement as the basis of education, we have to conduct classes using an electronic board, a projector, a computer, and show slides and videos. The organization of intermediate and final tests with the use of a computer for the greater involvement of students in modern technology, along with the teaching of other subjects,

also belongs to the teaching of Iranian history. Slides are very convenient and accessible for showing historical periods, the border of provinces, neighboring states of Iran, land and water borders of the country. For each topic, 10-15 slides have been prepared for presentation in class, which make the work of the teacher much easier. As they say in tradition: Hearing is like seeing. Maps and pictures of historical and cultural monuments are very important for students to remember and have a deeper understanding of Iran's history.

4. Ensuring the connection between subjects is one of the next requirements of the modern lesson, for this the teacher should try to find the points related to this or that subject of the educational topic of his subject and skillfully emphasize it in the process of explaining the new topic and other moments of the lesson. The subject of Iranian history can be taught in connection with Iranian mythology, the history of Persian literature, instruction and development of the Persian language, archeology, history of the Tajik people, etymology, and during the teaching of these subjects, the educational materials of Iranian history can also be used. The history textbook of Iran talks about the history of cities [1, p.24-26, 32, 35, 38, 46, 61, 70-71, 104-105, 113, 124...] and lists the historical and cultural monuments of these places. It is very important to be patient in the names of cities, rivers, mountains, and so that the subject remains in the minds of the students: «Khorasan is taken from Persian and means khur - sun, easy - rising place» [1, p.32]. «The word «Ardabil» is Avastian and consists of two words - ortho-holy and vil-shahr. Ortavil later became Ardavil, Ardabil» [1, p.61]. «Zoyandarud or Zindarud means a river that gives birth» [1, p.70] «The origin of the word Isfahan is known from the word «sipah» [1, p.71] «The word «Tabrez» is taken from the Pahlavi language «Turija» and means «current is to become», which is a reference to the springs of mineral water flowing from Sahand Lake» [1, p.105] «Ancient Greek historian - Herodotus tells that Dionku chose this place, which was called «Ikbaton» or «Wise», as his capital» [1, p.113], «Yazd» is related to «ezid, yazdan, izzat» and means praiseworthy, holy, good creator» [1, p.124]. Emphasis on etymology - the history of the origin of words in the mind of the reader improves the idea of the origin and development of languages, which is very important for students of the field of philology. By the way, it should be noted that the course of lectures is the main form of education, and through it, students get acquainted with some theoretical terms and concepts, historical periods of Iranian statehood, and important historical events. The rule of historical dynasties, desire for statehood, economy and life of people, individuals in the process of development of historical events are discussed and subjected to deeper analysis in practical lessons [2, p.2].

In this regard, it is worth noting that the subject of Iranian history also helps in improving students' language skills and provides strong inter-disciplinary connections. Also, it is important to link the subjects of history in the language learning of students regarding the history of the development of the modern Persian language. The vocabulary provided in the textbook is brief, and the texts of the book contain many words that need explanation, and the teacher can work with students on them in practical lessons to enrich their vocabulary and familiarity with cultures and dictionaries is of particular importance [2, p.17].

5. Organizing and carrying out practical work is also one of the parts of teaching the history of Iran. The credit system requires that the teacher should devote a certain part of the teaching of the subject to practical work, and this work is effective in organizing the students' activities. Students are given various tasks and their performance is monitored:

- performance of subject tests, phased and final test;
- drawing a map of the country of Iran and historical periods of the country's border [1,2,3];
- identifying major cities and showing their location on the map;
- marking historical and cultural monuments of masters on the drawn map of the country of Iran with symbols;

- collection of materials on historical figures, cultural monuments of the country and the history of their origin;

- preservation of the vocabulary presented in the educational manual and new vocabulary [2, p.176-177, 6,7].

These works provide practical help for strengthening the topics of the history of the country of Iran and expands the student's imagination and outlook. It is also worth noting that the organization of students' excursions to scientific-technical, economic-cultural exhibitions of Iran, which has become a tradition in our republic and the center of the region - the city of Khujand, helps to increase students' knowledge about the history of Iran.

Emomali Rahmon - the President of Tajikistan describes the development directions of the society as follows: «Development of society, sustainable economic development, ensuring national and state security, and generally achieving the world level of economy, technology, technology, science and culture, primarily depends on the development of education of citizens of Tajikistan [3, p.63]. The task of the teacher in implementing such requirements of the President of Tajikistan and the Ministry of Education of the Republic is very serious and responsible. The experience of teaching Arabic and Persian languages makes the teachers of this field to turn to new ways and methods of teaching in order to conduct the study in accordance with the requirements of the times, because the success of education requires keeping pace with the times.

References:

- [1]. Boboi, Parviz. *A complete history of Iran*. - Tehran. 1385, 246 p.
- [2]. *Methodical training complex. History of Iran*. - Khujand: *Light of Enlightenment*, 2015, 190 p.
- [3]. *Education is the future of Tajikistan*. - Khujand: *Publisher*, 2011. -22 p.
- [4]. *Letter of experts No. 3. A collection of scientific articles of the Faculty of Oriental Languages*. - Khujand: *Light of Knowledge*, 2010. 256p.
- [5]. Taslimi, Nasrullah. *History of Iranian art*. -Tehran: *Iran Textbook Printing and Publishing Company*, 1396, 138 p.